

Clinico-radiological Presentation of Pulmonary Tuberculosis in Diabetes Mellitus

Sanjay Tandon, Vivek Arora, S T Nagdeote

Department of Pulmonary Medicine, People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bhopal (MP)

ABSTRACT

An observational study was conducted to determine various clinical and radiological presentations of PTB in diabetes mellitus. All patients with PTB and Diabetes mellitus, newly detected (PND) or known diabetes (PKD), after a detailed history and thorough examination, were subjected to sputum smear examination for AFB, FBS, PPBS, HbA1c and Chest X-rays. Out of 78 patients with Pulmonary Tuberculosis and Diabetes mellitus, 46 (59.0%) patients were PND and 32 (41.0%) were PKD. There was male preponderance in both groups. 28% of the PKD patients had diabetes for 1-2 years. In the PND group, 31 (67.4%) patients were sputum smear positive, 15 (32.6%) were sputum smear negative. Forty six (100%) had cough with sputum and weight loss. Radiologically, 36 (78.3%) patients had lesions in lower lung field, 18 (39%) had minimal lesions, 33 (71.7%) had right sided lesions, 9 (19.6%) patients had multiple cavities and 31 (67.4%) patients did not have cavities. In the PKD group, Majority (69.6%) of the patients had poor glycemic control with HbA1C > 8, 23 (72%) patients were sputum smear positive, 9 (28%) patients were sputum smear negative, 32 (100%) patients had cough with sputum and weight loss. Radiologically, 25 (78%) patients had lesions in upper lung field and had right sided lesions, 12 (37.5%) patients had multiple cavities and 16 (50%) did not have cavities. Higher incidence of cavities was seen in the PKD group.

Patients with PTB and Diabetes were mostly male in both groups. Cough, sputum and weight loss were the most frequent symptoms in both PKD and PND. Fever was less common in both the groups. Both PND and PKD were more likely to be sputum positive (67.4% vs 72%) than sputum negative (32.6% vs 28%). Radiologically, there was a higher involvement of upper lung field (78%) in PKD group as compared with PND group and extent of lesion was almost similar in both the groups. Location of cavitory lesion over upper lung field (34.6% vs 6.4%) and multiple cavities (37.5% vs 19.6%) were more in PKD group as compared to PND group.

KEY WORDS: cavities, clinico-radiological, diabetes mellitus, lesion, pulmonary tuberculosis

INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis, which affects millions of people each year, is a major global health problem. It is still the main reason for mortality and morbidity in developing countries^[1]. The most common Diabetes mellitus globally is Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)^[2]. T2DM is recognized as a major risk factor for the progression of active Pulmonary Tuberculosis (PTB), although the mechanistic link between DM and Pulmonary Tuberculosis remains poorly understood^[3]. DM has been documented as a risk

factor for Tuberculosis for decades. According to the International Diabetes Federation 2013^[4], 382 million people were living with DM, of whom 80% were in low and middle-income countries and This is estimated to increase to 592 million by 2035. There were 65.1 million cases of DM in India that is estimated to rise upto 109 million by 2035^[4].

Higher prevalence of Pulmonary Tuberculosis in patients of DM is a well-known fact for a long time. However, higher prevalence of impaired glucose tolerance and DM in a tuberculous population is also being increasingly realized now and it becomes more relevant due to increased prevalence of DM in general population. Since, both Diabetes mellitus and Tuberculosis are major public health problems, we carried out the present study to determine various clinical and radiological presentations of Pulmonary Tuberculosis in patients with Diabetes mellitus in Central India. Specifically, we studied the differences in the clinico-radiological presentations between

Corresponding Author:

Dr Sanjay Tandon
Professor & Head,
Department of Pulmonary Medicine,
People's College of Medical Sciences
and Research Centre,
Bhanpur, Bhopal - 462037 (MP)
Phone No.: 0755-4004055
E-mail: pulmedph@gmail.com

Pulmonary Tuberculosis in newly detected Diabetes mellitus (PND) and Pulmonary Tuberculosis with known Diabetes mellitus (PKD).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was an observational study. All patients of Pulmonary Tuberculosis with DM who came to Pulmonary Medicine OPD of People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bhanpur (MP) were enrolled. The study was conducted from January 2018 to June 2019. Group 1 comprised patients with Pulmonary Tuberculosis with newly detected DM type-2 (PND) and Group 2 had patients with Pulmonary Tuberculosis with known DM type-2 (PKD).

The Inclusion criteria were: Patients with age more than 18 years of either gender; Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of Pulmonary Tuberculosis; Patients with known DM type-2 on glucose-lowering medications; Patients with newly detected DM 2 and Patients and/or his/her legally acceptable representative willing to provide voluntary written informed consent to participate in the study.

The Exclusion Criteria were: Patients with age less than 18 years; Patients living with HIV and AIDS; Patients with any type of malignancy, Pregnant women; Patients with extrapulmonary tuberculosis; Patients with DM type-1 and Patients and/or his/her legally acceptable representative not willing to provide their voluntary written informed consent to participate in the study.

All presumed TB patients who had any one of the following: cough > 2 weeks, fever > 2 weeks, significant weight loss, hemoptysis, any abnormality in chest X-ray were asked to submit first sputum sample (spot sample) and next morning sputum sample for AFB. Diagnosis of Pulmonary Tuberculosis was made by sputum smear examination for AFB by Ziehl-Neelsen technique and in sputum smear negative patients, diagnosis was made by molecular test i.e. Cartridge Based Nucleic Acid Amplification Test (CBNAAT).

DM status was assessed after reviewing the available records with the patients and/ or their self-reported history regarding DM status. All patients with newly diagnosed Pulmonary Tuberculosis underwent FBS, PPBS and HbA1c as a part of screening and diagnosis of Diabetes was made according to 'Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes 2017'.

Radiological evaluation with plain CXR was done to note the location of lesions, the extent of lesions, location of cavity and number of cavities.

Extent of disease was classified as follows:

- 1) Minimally advanced: lesion which was slight to moderate in density with no demonstrable cavitation, the total volume of lung on one side, present above the second chondrosternal junction, and spine of the fourth thoracic vertebra.
- 2) Moderately advanced: Disseminated lesions of slight to moderate density that extended to the total volume of one lung or equivalent in both lungs; and a total diameter of cavitations, if present, less than 4 cm.
- 3) Far advanced: lesion more extensive than moderately advanced.

Both right and left lung parenchyma were divided into upper and lower lung fields by a horizontal line drawn across the hilum.

The data was entered into Microsoft Excel for analysis. Online statistical software was used for calculating p values. Intra group mean comparisons were done using paired 't' test. Association between two non-parametric variables was done using the Pearson Chi-square test.

RESULTS:

Out of 78 patients with Pulmonary Tuberculosis and DM, 46 (59.0%) patients were in PND group and 32 (41.0%) were in PKD group.

The mean age in PND group was 49.67 ± 12.17 years and in PKD group was 53.41 ± 9.22 years. The difference was found to be statistically not significant ($p=0.147$). There were 15 (32.6%) females and 31 (67.4%) males in the PND group. In the PKD group, there were 7 (21.9%) females and 25 (78.1%) males. There was a male preponderance in both the groups. TB with diabetes was present in 32 alcoholics (41%) and 45 smokers (57.7%). Smoking (62.5% vs 54.3%) and alcoholism (50% vs 34.8%) were more present in the PKD group as compared to PND group. In PKD group, there were 5 (15.6%) patients with duration of diabetes of ≤ 1 year, 9 (28.1%) patients had 1-2 years, 5 (15.6%) patients for 2-3 years, 7 (21.9%) patients for 4-5 years, 4 (12.5%) patients for 6-10 years and 2 (6.3%) patients for more than 10 years. Majority of the patients had duration of diabetes of 1-2 years, followed by a duration of 4-5 years (Table 1).

Majority 31 (67.4%), of the patients were sputum positive and 15 (32.6%) were sputum negative in PND (p value=0.002). In PKD, majority 23 (71.9%) of patients were sputum positive and 9 (30.8%) patients were sputum negative in old DM ($p=0.001$).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics.

Age	PND	PKD	Total
<30 years	2(4.3%)	0 (0.0%)	2(2.6%)
31-40 years	10(21.7%)	2(6.3%)	12(15.4%)
41-50 years	15(32.6%)	11 (34.4%)	26(33.3%)
51-60 years	9(19.6%)	12(37.5%)	21(26.9%)
>60 years	10(21.7%)	7(21.9%)	17(21.8%)
Total	46(100.0%)	32(100%)	78(100%)
Mean Age	49.67 ± 12.17	53.41 ± 9.22	p = 0.147
Gender	PND	PKD	Total
Female	15(32.6%)	7(21.9%)	22(28.2%)
Male	31(67.4%)	25(78.1%)	56(71.8%)
Total	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Personal Habits	PND	PKD	Total
Smoking	25(54.3%)	20(62.5%)	45(57.7%)
Alcohol	16(34.8%)	16(50.0%)	32(41.0%)
Duration of Diabetes	Number	Percentage	
≤1 year	5	15.6	
1-2 years	9	28.1	
2-3 years	5	15.6	
4-5 years	7	21.9	
6-10 years	4	12.5	
>10 years	2	6.3	
Total	32	100.0	

In both groups, most common symptoms were cough with sputum and weight loss which were present in all 78 patients (100%) followed by fever (69.2%), chest pain (29.5%), shortness of breath (25.6%), night sweats (20.5%) and haemoptysis (16.7%). The presenting complaints were similar in both the groups (Table 2).

Radiological profile of TB diabetics. Majority of the PND patients (78.3%) had lesions in lower lung field whereas in PKD group, majority of the patients (78.1%) had lesions in upper lung field. The location of lesions with regard to lung field in both the groups was distributed nearly equally. In the PND group, most (39.1%) of the patients had minimal lesion followed by moderate advanced (34.8%) and far advanced (26%) whereas in PKD group, most (40.6%) of the patients had moderately advanced lesions followed by minimal lesion (37.5%) and far advanced (22%). The extent of lesion was almost equal in both groups (Table 3).

Higher percentage of cavity (34.4%) was seen in the upper lung field in PKD group (p=0.002) and lower lung field (26.1%) in PND group. In PND group, 15 (32.6%) patients had cavities and 31 (67.4%) patients had no cavities while in the PKD group, 16 (50.0%) patients had cavities and 16 (50.0%) patients had no cavities. Higher incidence of cavities was seen in the PKD group. Multiple cavities were commoner in the PKD than in the PND group.

DISCUSSION:

This was a hospital based observational study done over a period of one and half year at the Department of Pulmonary Medicine, People's Hospital, Bhopal. Screening of all patients for Pulmonary Tuberculosis and Diabetes mellitus coming to Pulmonary Medicine OPD of People's

Table 2: Clinical profile of patients.

Sputum for AFB	PND	PKD	Total
Scanty	4(8.7%)	3(9.4%)	7(9.0%)
1+	8(17.4%)	6(18.8%)	14(17.9%)
2+	8(17.4%)	9(28.1%)	17(21.8%)
3+	11(23.9%)	5(15.6%)	16(20.5%)
Negative	15(32.6%)	9(28.1%)	24(30.8%)
Total	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Sputum Positive Cases	31(67.4%)	23(71.9%)	54(69.2%)
Sputum for AFB	PND	PKD	Total
Negative	15(32.6%)	9(28.1%)	24(30.8%)
Sputum Positive Cases	31(67.4%)	23(71.9%)	54(69.2%)
Total	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Fisher's Exact Test (Sputum -ve & Sputum +ve)		0.002	0.001
Presenting Complains	PND	PKD	Total
Cough with sputum	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Fever	36(78.3%)	18(56.3%)	54(69.2%)
Loss of appetite	38(82.6%)	24(75.0%)	62(79.5%)
Weight Loss	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Haemoptysis	7(15.2%)	6(18.8%)	13(16.7%)
Chest pain	14(30.4%)	9(28.1%)	23(29.5%)
Shortness of breath	12(26.1%)	8(25.0%)	20(25.6%)
Night sweats	11(23.9%)	5(15.6%)	16(20.5%)

Hospital was done. The study was conducted on those patients with a confirmed diagnosis of Pulmonary Tuberculosis with DM.

Out of 78 patients with Pulmonary Tuberculosis and Diabetes mellitus, 46 (59.0%) patients were PND and 32 (41.0%) were PKD. In our study, most of the TB diabetics (48.7%) were more than 50 years of age and there was a male preponderance (67.4% vs 78.1%) in both groups. Smoking (62.5% vs 54.3%) and alcoholism (50% vs 34.8%) were more in the PKD group as compared to PND group. In the PKD group, 28.% had a duration of diabetes for 1-2 years. Majority (67.4%) of the patients were sputum positive and 32.6% were sputum negative in PND group (p value=0.002). In PKD group, majority (71.9%) of the patients were sputum positive and 30.8% patients were sputum negative in PKD group (p=0.001). The predominant symptoms in both groups were cough with sputum and weight loss which were present in all 78 patients (100%) followed

by fever (69.2%), chest pain (29.5%), shortness of breath (25.6%), night sweats (20.5%) and haemoptysis (16.7%).

Radiologically, PND had predominantly lower lung field (78.3%) involvement while PKD had upper lung field (78%) involvement. In PND, most (39%) of the patients had minimal lesion whereas in PKD, most (40.6%) of the patients had moderately advanced lesions. Majority of the patients in both groups did not have cavity (60.3%). Multiple cavities (37.5%) were commoner in PKD as compared to the PND (19.6%). PKD had more cavities (34.4%) in upper lung field whereas PND had more cavities in lower lung field (26.1%).

Gender: There was a male preponderance in both PND and PKD groups (67.4% vs 78.1%). Other workers in India and abroad have also reported similar male predominance. One possible explanation for this male predominance may be that in most countries young men and elderly usually have more social labour

Table 3: Radiological findings of patients.

Location of Lesion	PND	PKD	p value
Upper lung field	27(58.7%)	25(78.1%)	0.091
Lower lung field	36(78.3%)	24(75.0%)	0.789
Upper+Lower lung field	17(37.0%)	17(53.1%)	0.172
Extent of Lesion	PND	PKD	Total
Minimal lesion	18(39.1%)	12(37.5%)	30(38.5%)
Moderate advanced	16(34.8%)	13(40.6%)	29(37.2%)
Far advanced	12(26.1%)	7(21.9%)	19(24.4%)
Total	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Location of Cavity	PND	PKD	p value
Upper lung field	3(6.5%)	11(34.4%)	0.002
Lower lung field	12(26.1%)	9(28.1%)	1.000, NS
Upper plus Lower field	45(97.8%)	30(93.8%)	0.565, NS
Number of cavities	PND	PKD	Total
Single cavity	6(13.0%)	4(12.5%)	10(12.8%)
Multiple cavities	9(19.6%)	12(37.5%)	21(26.9%)
No cavities	31(67.4%)	16(50.0%)	47(60.3%)
Total	46(100.0%)	32(100.0%)	78(100.0%)
Total cavities present	15(32.6%)	16(50.0%)	31(39.7%)

activities and more stress than women, thus favouring the transmission of tuberculosis.

Duration of Diabetes: In our study, 41% patients had previously diagnosed DM. In the previously diagnosed DM, most of the them (28.1%) had a duration of diabetes of 1-2 years followed by 22% patients who had diabetes for 4-5 years.

Results of sputum for AFB: Majority(67.4%) of the patients were sputum positive and 32.6% were sputum negative in PND group ($p=0.002$). In PKD, majority (71.9%) of patients were sputum positive and 30.8% patients were sputum negative ($p=0.001$). Most of the patients (21.5%) in both groups had grade 2 sputum positivity.

In our study, sputum positivity was equal in both PND and PKD group (67.4% vs 72%). The reason why large proportion of patients were sputum positive in PKD group was that they had more cavitory type Pulmonary TB (37.5% vs 19.6%) and more advanced lesions (40.6% vs 26.1%).

Singla et al (2006)^[6] and (Dooley et al 2009)^[7] in their studies found that diabetes was an independent risk factor associated with more numerous AFB on sputum smear.

Presenting Complaints: In our study, most common symptoms in TB Diabetics were cough with sputum

and weight loss which were present in all 78 patients (100%) followed by fever (69.2%), chest pain (29.5%) shortness of breath (25.6%), night sweats (20.5%) and haemoptysis (16.7%). The presenting complaints were similar in both the groups. Reider HL, et al (1999)^[8], Crofton J et al (2009)^[9] and Girardi E et al (2017)^[10] in their studies reported that cough was the most common symptom of respiratory disease, including TB, and haemoptysis appeared in about 20% of TB patients.

Jovana M Pavlovic et al (2018)^[11] in their study showed that cough stayed as a dominant symptom of pulmonary TB in patients with DM.

Radiological findings:

Location of lesions according to lung field: As for roentgenographic abnormality, in our study, the location of lesions was almost same in both PND and PKD groups. However, there was a higher involvement of lower lung field (78.3%) in PND; and upper lung field (78.1%) in PKD group.

Extent of lesion: In our study PND in, most (39%) of the patients had minimal lesion whereas in PKD, most (40.6%) of the patients had moderately advanced lesion. The extent of lesion was almost equal in both groups.

Ezung et al (2002)^[12] in their study found that out of the 27 patients of PTB with Diabetes, 11 (40.7%) had minimal lesions, 7 (25.9%) had moderate lesions and 9 (33.3%) patients had far advanced lesions.

Cavitary lesion: Majority of the patients in both groups did not have cavity (60.3%). Multiple cavities (37.5%) were common in PKD group as compared to the PND (19.6%). AB Shrivastava et al (2016)^[13] in their study found a higher prevalence of cavitary lung disease in TB with Diabetes (83%) as compared to PTB patients without diabetes.

Location of cavity: PKD group had more cavities (34.4%) in upper lung field whereas PND group had more cavities in lower lung field (26.1%).

Bashar et al in their study found predominant upper lung field involvement but contrary to this, Morris et al and Bacakoglu et al found predominant lower lung field involvement.

Chiang et al (2014)^[17] in their study found that proportions of DM patients with cavitary lesions over upper lung field and multiple cavities were greater in patients with poor glycaemic control than good glycaemic control (HbA1c > 9%).

According to Podell B K et al. (2012)^[18], increased frequency of pulmonary cavitary lesions in diabetic patients with poor glycemic control could be related to reduced expression of Th 1-related cytokines.

CONCLUSION:

Patients with PTB and Diabetes were mostly male in both groups. Cough, sputum and weight loss were the most frequent symptoms in both PKD and PND. Fever was less common in both the groups. Both PND and PKD were more likely to be sputum positive (67.4% vs 72%) than sputum negative (32.6% vs 28%). Radiologically, there was a higher involvement of upper lung field (78%) in PKD as compared with PND and extent of lesion was almost similar in both the groups. Upper lung field (34.6% vs 6.4%) and multiple cavities (37.5% vs 19.6%) were more common in PKD as compared to PND.

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